

**A STUDY OF STUDY HABBITTS OF NINTH STANDARD
STUDENTS OF ENGLISH MEDIUM IN DHULE CITY**

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Importance of Study :

Study is the most important part of every student's life because study is directly related to academic performance decides future path of student's life. So many misconcepts are carried out by students at the time of study e.g. a student thinks that only reading means studying , only few days before examination are proper for study, only to qualify the examination and getting good numbers is the objective of study etc. And most important thing which is commonly appears is that for many students study is the hectic work.

Need of Study :

By doing this study we can find out that whether students have good study habits or not ? This statistics about study habits of a student should useful for teachers to guide their students properly, by developing good study habits in students we can also increase their understanding power, longetivity of memory to acquire knowledge, much more study can possible in less time and in less efforts, discipline about study should be increased.

So as per above mentioned importance and need, it is very essential to carry out research work about study habits of students.

Statement of the problem :

A Study of study habbits of ninth standard students of English medium in Dhule city.

Objectives :

- (1) To find out study habits of 9th standard students of English medium school in Dhule City.
- (2) To find out study of boys studying in 9th standard students of English medium school in Dhule city.
- (3) To find out study habits of girls studying in 9th standard students of English medium school in Dhule city.

Null Hypothesis : There is no difference in study habits of boys and girls studying in 9th standard in English medium school of Dhule city.

Operational definitions :

Dhule City : A district place located at the Panjra river bank in north Maharashtra.

9th Standard : A class situated after 8th class and before 10th class in 10+2+3 pattern of education.

English Medium Schools : A type of schools in which medium of instructions are in English.

A) Scope :

- 1) Research based on data collection in 2015-2016.

B) Limitations : Difficulties arising at the time of research are the limitations of research.

- i) The researcher had decided to collect the data during 20th Dec to 30th Dec 2015 but due to Christmas holidays he could not collect it so the researcher collected the data in Jan 2016.

Research Methodology :

Survey method :

Survey research method is involving the use of questionnaires and/or statistical surveys to gather data about people and their thoughts and behaviors.

Population :

Population is a group of individuals or items that share one or more characteristics from which data can be gathered and analyzed. There are near about 9 to 10 english

medium school in Dhule city. Around 500 students are studying in Std. IX in english medium school in Dhule city.

Sample :

A set of elements drawn from and analyzed to estimate the characteristics of population is called sampling. For the research we have selected 2 English medium schools and 200 students studying in this school. From the 200 students selected 100 students are girls and 100 are boys.

Research Tools :

For this research 'Study Habits Inventory' test is used. This test is prepared by Shri M. N. Palsane from Pune University. There are 45 questions are asked in this test. Every question has three options (Always or mostly, sometimes, rarely or never) and score points 2,1,0 are given for each option the student has to choose any one option. The sum of the score points is the raw score of the students.

Methodology

Test was administered on selected sample. After data collection score are calculated as per manual and statistical analysis was done.

The Analysis of collected data and its interpretation :

Objective wise data analysis :

Objective 1 :

To find out the study habits of boys and girls studying in 9th std. in English medium in Dhule city.

Raw Score	Interpretation	No.of Students	%
Above 74	Excellent Study habits	10	5
64-74	Good Study habits	77	39
53-63	Average study habits	84	42
42-52	Unsatisfactory study habits	1	0
Below 42	Very unstatistactory	1	0

Objective 2 :

To find out the study habits of boys in 9th std. in English medium in Dhule city.

Raw Score	Interpretation	No.of Students	%
Above 74	Excellent Study habits	5	5
64-74	Good Study habits	30	30
53-63	Average study habits	50	50
42-52	Unsatisfactory study habits	15	15
Below 42	Very unsatisfactory	0	0

Objective 3 :

To find out the study habits of girls studying in 9th std. in English medium in Dhule city.

Raw Score	Interpretation	No.of Students	%
Above 74	Excellent Study habits	5	5
64-74	Good Study habits	47	47
53-63	Average study habits	34	34
42-52	Unsatisfactory study habits	13	13
Below 42	Very unsatisfactory	1	1

Hypothesis wise Data Analysis :

Null hypothesis : There is no difference in study habits of boys and girls studying in 9th standard in English Medium of Dhule city.

Vari ables	N	Calcula ted t	df	Level of significance	Value of 't' by table	Calcul ated 't' and table t	signi ficance	Null hypothesis
Boys	100	1.04	198	0.05	1.97	1.04<1.97	Not Signi ficant	Accepted
Girls	100							

Calculated value of 't' is less than value of table t, so the difference in both groups is not-significant. In such condition Null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusions :

- (i) There is no difference in study habits of boys and girls studying in 9th Std. in English medium in Dhule city. Means both boys and girls have same study habits.
- (ii) 5% students have excellent study habits.
39% students have good study habits.
42% students have average study habits.
14% students have unsatisfactory study habits.
0% students have very unsatisfactory study habits.

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